
**THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF ORGANIZING PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE
BASED ON THE INNOVATION APPROACH IN FUTURE PRIMARY
EDUCATION STUDENTS**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7893447>

Badalov Dilmurod Abdikhalilovich

Termiz University of Economics and Service

Teacher of the "Social and Humanities" department

Phone: 93-761-17-11 e-mail: dilmurodbadalov907@gmail.com

Annotation.

This article describes the process of preparing future specialists to work in new conditions, pedagogical innovation, innovative approach, goals, tasks, stages of students' pedagogical practice, organization and conduct of professional practice in the higher education system.

Key words.

future specialists, pedagogical innovation, innovative approach, pedagogical practice.

The preparation of students for pedagogical activity in pedagogical higher education institutions is a complex process, and its rational implementation serves to ensure the professional maturity of the future pedagogic staff. It is known that the training of personnel in a specific direction and specialty is based on accumulated experience, educational standards regulated on the basis of scientific research, as well as normative documents that provide it legally, a system of educational and methodical literature. based on So, in this case, the training of personnel is carried out with a long view. This is the main component of personnel training and it is given state importance in our country. At the same time, there is also the question of how to use it in the educational process, and we have made a lot of progress in this regard. It can be seen that there are two interrelated processes in the training of highly educated personnel, one of which is strategic and the other is tactical.

Pedagogical innovation is a process that prepares future specialists to work in new conditions, it consists in making qualitative changes in education based on previously acquired knowledge and making a new approach to achieving high efficiency.

The ultimate goal of the concept of "innovative approach" is to introduce changes and updates that guarantee the result of the educational process in the field of education. Pedagogical innovations are used in order to make positive changes in the relevant field and achieve high-quality results.

Pedagogical practice of students of pedagogical higher education institutions is an important factor in training professional pedagogical personnel. After all, if knowledge is a treasure, without a doubt, the key that opens its door is practice, practical education.

Globalization, especially in connection with the acceleration of the process of further reforms in pedagogical education, the emergence of modern teaching technologies and the widespread use of information and communication technologies in practice, this problem has become more acute. The training of specialists in the higher education system is mainly two important links:

consists of scientific-theoretical and practical training.

Practical training consists of the continuity and consistency of the application of theoretical knowledge and skills, and depends to a large extent on the effectiveness of the qualified production practice organized in the educational process.

Based on the innovative approach, the pedagogical practice of students in the works carried out by Russian pedagogues N.V.Kuzmina, M.B.Klarin, VASlastenin and Uzbek scientists B.A. approach, grounding of innovative ideas and their effective implementation in practice are researched. Uzbek scientists N. Saidahmedov, N. Azizkhojaeva, Sh. Shodmonov, G. Baubekova, G. Khalikova, and others look at pedagogical innovations as a special form of best practice [1.11].

It is known that the production practice of students, which is an important part of the training of personnel in the fields of undergraduate education - modern methods in science and technology, technology and production, having studied experiences, professional skills and practical skills is based on formation.

The results of pedagogical observations show that there are several shortcomings in the organization and conduct of professional practice in the higher education system. Due to the fact that the integrity of theory and practice is not ensured in the process of higher education, and the training of students in production enterprises is not effectively organized, most of the graduates, instead of becoming ready specialists, after getting a job, learn their profession and specialty again. learning, as well as the fact that the mechanism of monitoring the

quality of education does not meet modern requirements, there is a shortage of qualified pedagogues and management personnel in educational institutions.

Non-compliance of the practice software with modern requirements; insufficient use of effective methods of innovative technologies in the organization of practice; such problems as the insufficiently developed system for evaluating the results of practice require an innovative approach to its organization and implementation.

Concepts such as "Innovative approach", "Innovative activity", "Innovative pedagogy" emerging in the development of modern education are needed

and their purpose is to introduce changes and updates that guarantee the result of the educational process in the field of education. In the conditions of innovative technologies, updating the content of the student's practical and professional training, developing ways to use innovative technologies in the organization of professional practices is considered one of the urgent pedagogical problems.

It is known that innovative educational technologies are forms, methods and technologies used in the field of education or in the educational process to solve existing problems based on a new approach and guarantee a more effective result than before [2.275].

These technologies create an environment of independent work and two-way communication in the formation of professional knowledge and skills of students

helps to develop a student's cognitive abilities and creative abilities.

Taking into account the professional interests and wishes of students during pedagogical practice, conducting propaedeutic work with students, modern educational problems in order to increase the level of pedagogical culture of students

organization of various scientific-methodological activities, determining their inclinations and interests.

At the end of each stage of pedagogical practice, students prepare and submit a diary of an intern-student for verification, at the final conferences, students present a report on the completion of pedagogical practice, research works, creative projects. prepare reports announcing the results.

Pedagogical practice is the main part of the educational-pedagogical process in training future teachers. Pedagogical practice is carried out in accordance with the model and working curriculum. The content of pedagogical practice depends on the type of practice and corresponds to the program developed in the department.

Pedagogical practice is organized separately from training sessions. Pedagogical practice can be done by students in educational institutions that have a contract with a higher education institution. In some cases, students of the graduate course are allowed to do active pedagogical practice in the educational institutions where they plan to work.

Pedagogical practice is the main and important part of the system of professional training of a future specialist. Pedagogical practice is a process that connects the student's theoretical education and future independent activity and ensures the formation of professional skills and qualifications, and is considered a school of initial experience.

The purpose of pedagogical practice is to prepare future teachers for professional activities, to test the acquired knowledge in practice, to feel the responsibility of pedagogical activities and to form the skills to work on oneself, as well as to improve the work of experienced teachers. consists of learning. In determining the purpose of pedagogical practice, we proceeded from general didactic goals, as well as from the uniqueness of the content of educational and pedagogical activity.

The general didactic goal of educational and pedagogical practice can be defined as follows: organization of all types of practice at all stages of pedagogical education, continuous practical professional-pedagogical activity of students (based on the requirements set for the level of practical training of graduates of higher education institutions) and should be aimed at ensuring consistent acquisition.

In accordance with the goals, based on the need to form special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, and practical training in the students, the main issues are expressed. Acquired theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications should allow independent implementation of educational and pedagogical activities.

Tasks of pedagogical practice:

Cultivating students' interest in the teaching profession;

Formation of a whole understanding of pedagogical activity;

Formation of pedagogical skills and qualifications;

Creating experience in pedagogical activities.

The purpose and scope of the types of practice (educational practice, pedagogical practice, organizational-pedagogical practice, production practice, pre-

diploma practice) are determined by the State educational standards in the field of education "Pedagogy and psychology".

From our point of view, this way of expressing the goal is, firstly, not practical enough, and secondly, the goal should be defined separately for each type of practice.

In the conditions of modern education, monitoring and evaluation of knowledge, skills and qualifications of practitioners should acquire a new meaning.

It is advisable to organize the assessment of the practitioner's mastery during the study of each module. In order to determine the results of the practitioner's mastery in practice, it is possible to give different versions of the tasks at the end of each module.

In the final evaluation of the practice, it is appropriate to take into account the average value of the points collected for the modules and the activity and professional qualities of the practitioner during the reporting period.

The purpose of our research work is to develop a method of didactically correct design, planning and implementation of the educational and pedagogical practice program and to implement it in practice. Such educational and pedagogical practice program allows to eliminate the conflicts indicated above [3.68].

Pedagogical practice is carried out in three stages.

Stage 1 - familiarization-pedagogical practice. It is carried out during the second 2 weeks. During the internship, students mainly get acquainted with the work of the educational institution and submit a report in the prescribed manner.

2nd stage - educational and pedagogical practice. This will be done at the educational institution for 2 weeks. In it, students are held in an educational institution

they get acquainted with all legal and regulatory documents and the work of teachers of specialized subjects.

3rd stage - active pedagogical practice. It will last 4 weeks. In the process of active pedagogical practice, together with the preparation of students for training sessions,

makes a plan of spiritual and moral educational activities and organizes interviews. To himself

conducts a pedagogical-psychological diagnosis in the attached group.

In addition, within the framework of pedagogical practice, the practicing student not only carries out educational and moral-ethical educational work, but

also from the point of view of the methodology of teaching science, conducts creative-research work in a number of the following directions:

- the equipment of specialized science rooms, the presence and location of visual aids, the existence of a teaching-methodological complex in science;
- availability of practice rooms for specialized subjects, their equipment; the content of the stand and posters, technical safety of the classroom and meet aesthetic requirements;
- the availability and maintenance of technical means of teaching in the rooms of specialization and educational practice;
- they get acquainted with the analysis of educational-methodical complexes available in the specialty and training practice rooms, the level of class and extracurricular activities.

Also, he analyzes sample and working curricula, study guides and textbooks from the specialty subjects, studies the teaching style of the teachers of the specialty subjects. At the end of each pedagogical practice, students write a report on the work done during the practice period and defend it.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be said that the organization of practice and evaluation in pedagogical education based on an innovative approach not only ensures the effectiveness of practice results, but also creates the basis for training highly qualified teachers who can compete in the labor market. Pedagogical observations and results of our activities made it possible to formulate the following conclusions and recommendations [5.220]:

REFERENCES:

1. Очиллов М. Янги педагогик технологиялар. - Қарши: 'Насаф', 2000. 11 - бет.
2. Каримова М. Мутахассисни касбий тайёрлаш жараёнини моделлаштириш // Общество и инновации. - 2021. - Т. 2. - №. 8/S. - С. 274-282. <https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/index>
3. Авлиякулов Н.Х., Мусаева Н.Н. Педагогик технологиялар. - Тошкент: 'Фан ва технология', 2008. 91-бет.
4. Dilafruz RAFIKOVA, Mukaddas KARIMOVA Regulatory and legal support of the modernization process in the higher pedagogical education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Society and innovations Journal home page: <https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/index> 2021 yil sentyabr. 214-226 b.

5.Муслимов Н.А., Усмонбоева М.Х., Сайфуров Д.М., Тураев А.Б..Иновацион таълим технологиялари. Тошкент: 'Sano-standart' 2015